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Speech intelligibility and spatial release from masking in anechoic and reverberant rooms: Comparison between German-speaking and Mandarin-speaking listeners

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ABSTRACT:

This study investigates the effects of masker and reverberation on the speech intelligibility and spatial release from masking (SRM) for tonal and non-tonal language speakers. Speech reception thresholds (SRTs) were measured in native Mandarin-Chinese-speaking (CMNS) and German-speaking (GS) normal hearing (NH) listeners using matrix sentence tests, in three virtual rooms with different reverberation times. Simulated bilateral cochlear implant (BiCI) users were also assessed under the same conditions. Reverberation had a stronger impact on SRTs and SRM with the international female fluctuating masker (IFFM) than with speech-shaped noise (SSN) for both NH groups and was more detrimental for simulated BiCI users. CMNS NH listeners exhibited significantly lower SRTs than GS listeners, but GS listeners showed larger SRM for IFFM. Reverberation exhibited a non-linear effect on SRT and SRM, especially for IFFM. CMNS listeners experienced greater SRT degradation in co-located conditions with reverberation. While both groups showed similar SRM degradation in the small reverberant room, CMNS listeners showed lower SRM without any further detrimental effect of stronger reverberation. Both CI processing and reverberation had a greater impact on SRTs for CMNS than GS. The simulated CMNS BiCI listeners showed lower SRTs than GS listeners for SSN, but SRM did not differ significantly.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to cope with challenging acoustical scenarios, often denoted as the "cocktail party" problem (e.g., [Cherry, 1953](#)), was extensively studied in the past (for an overview, see [Bronkhorst, 2000, 2015](#)) with focus on Western languages. In such scenarios, speech intelligibility can be substantially improved when the target speaker is spatially separated from interfering masker sources ([Cherry, 1953](#); [Plomp, 1976](#); [Yost et al., 1996](#); [Peissig and Kollmeier, 1997](#); [Bronkhorst, 2000](#)) in comparison to co-located target and maskers. This improvement is typically denoted as spatial release from masking (SRM) involving binaural spatial cues, such as different interaural level and time differences (ILDs and ITDs) for the spatially separated target and masker, as well as better ear glimpsing ([Brungart and Iyer, 2012](#); [Glyde et al., 2013](#); [Best et al., 2015](#)). In addition to such spatial cues, level cues (e.g., [Brungart, 2001](#)), voice/timbre cues ([Iverson, 1995](#); [Brungart, 2001](#)), temporal fine structure (TFS) or pitch cues (e.g., [Moore, 2008, 2021](#); [Hu et al., 2024](#)) can also be helpful for the listeners to separate the target from the masker.

Since everyday communication typically takes place in enclosed spaces, target speech might be additionally interfered by reverberation. Previous studies have shown reduced SRM due to impaired binaural cues in reverberant compared to anechoic situations ([Plomp, 1976](#); [Kidd et al., 2005](#); [Marrone et al., 2008](#); [Lavandier and Culling, 2010](#); [Biberger and Ewert, 2019](#)). Nevertheless, listeners still benefit from spatial separation of target and masker sounds compared to co-located configurations.

In co-located situations, where binaural cues are largely absent, monaural cues (e.g., pitch, spectral composition) become essential for separating the target from the maskers, which may also be degraded by reverberation. It is known that reverberation can alter the TFS of the speech by smearing dynamic changes in the rapid variations of the waveform over time and attenuate or flatten the temporal envelope (or amplitude) modulations by filling in the less intense portions of the waveform ([Houtgast et al., 1980](#)). In this regard, according to [Bolt and MacDonald \(1949\)](#), speech intelligibility in reverberant rooms is stronger impaired by overlap-masking, referring to masking effects of late sound reflections, than by self-masking, referring to effects of earlier reflections. In reverberant situations with target speech presented in a fluctuating masker, temporal smearing of the

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masker lowers the chance to listen in to the dips, which additionally lowers speech intelligibility. Previous studies have successfully predicted the impact of reverberation on speech intelligibility for non-tonal languages using amplitude modulation (AM) processing in auditory models (e.g., Steeneken and Houtgast, 1980; Jørgensen and Dau, 2011; Bib Berger and Ewert, 2016). As a result, the impact of reverberation on SRM may reflect an interaction between spatially separated and co-located configurations. Previous speech intelligibility studies with non-tonal languages have shown that the reduced SRM in reverberant environments can be often attributed to higher SRTs in spatially separated (e.g., Plomp, 1976; Marrone *et al.*, 2008) configurations, while co-located configurations are less affected by reverberation.

Unlike most Western languages, where pitch primarily conveys emotion rather than distinguishing word meaning, tones in Mandarin and other tonal languages are crucial for intelligibility. In addition to the fundamental frequency, speakers of tonal language may rely on acoustic cues, such as overall intensity, duration, and amplitude envelope to distinguish lexical tone (Whalen and Xu, 1992; Fu and Zeng, 2000; Kuo *et al.*, 2008; Hu *et al.*, 2018b, 2022a; Chen *et al.*, 2025).

Several studies (e.g., Wong *et al.*, 2007; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2016; Du *et al.*, 2019) suggest that lower frequency regions are more important in Cantonese and Mandarin than in English, necessitating adaptations of the band-importance function in the speech intelligibility index (SII, ANSI-S3.5, 1997) for reasonable speech intelligibility predictions of tonal languages. However, on the other hand, common building materials and finishes typically absorb less sound at low frequencies than at high frequencies, leading to strong sound reflections and longer reverberation times at lower frequencies.

The detrimental effect of reverberation on both temporal envelope and fine structure cues has been studied in both animals (Sayles and Winter, 2008) and humans (Darwin and Hukin, 2000; Ruggles and Shinn-Cunningham, 2011; Srinivasan and Zahorik, 2014). Most of these studies support that the temporal envelope cues are more degraded than fine-structure cues by reverberation. Considering the frequency-dependent reverberation time and given the more important role of pitch and TFS information in tonal than in non-tonal languages (Xu and Pfingst, 2003; Cabrera *et al.*, 2014; Qi *et al.*, 2017), reverberation may have different impacts on the speech intelligibility of tonal and non-tonal languages, especially in co-located configurations where binaural cues (ILDs and ITDs) were absent.

Kang (1998) compared the speech intelligibility of native Mandarin-speaking and English-speaking listeners in both reverberant and ambient noise (white noise). He found that the decrease in word intelligibility caused by reverberation was greater in English than in Mandarin, while the decrease in word intelligibility caused by noise was greater in Mandarin than in English. The corridor and seminar room tested in the study of Kang (1998) had a limited range of early decay times of 0.6–1.3 s at 0.5–1 kHz; therefore, Kang (1998) suggested to use a greater early decay time

range in future investigations of differences between Mandarin and English. Moreover, for a fixed signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR), the differences in intelligibility between the two languages are dependent on specific test materials and the spectrum of the background noise. It is necessary to use sentences developed for a more general comparison between languages.

Regarding the use of auditory pitch and AM features for speech intelligibility in tonal and non-tonal languages, cochlear implants (CIs) pose specific challenges while providing significant benefits for individuals with severe to profound hearing loss by restoring access to speech sounds (Wilson and Dorman, 2008; Roche and Hansen, 2015; Gifford, 2020). CI users have been reported to face challenges in pitch perception because contemporary CIs fail to provide normal pitch perception (Hagerman and Kinnefors, 1995) due to primarily using envelope-based processors without delivering the true fine-structure cues. However, the TFS is more important for pitch perception (Smith *et al.*, 2002; Xu and Pfingst, 2003) than the temporal envelope. As semantic information in tonal languages is also conveyed through pitch contour, tonal language speaking CI users might perform more poorly than non-tonal language speaking CI users in noise (Mao and Xu, 2017). Similar effects as those observed in CI users have been found in normal-hearing (NH) listeners using simulated CI processing using a noise vocoder (Xu *et al.*, 2002). Because the noise vocoder removes TFS cues from the signal while preserving AM cues, it also has been widely used to investigate their relative contribution to speech intelligibility (Shannon *et al.*, 1995; Smith *et al.*, 2002).

Taken together, the effect of reverberation on tonal and non-tonal languages could depend on the amount of reverberation, the type of maskers, and the spatial configuration of the target and masker sources. Based on our knowledge, no study has been conducted to compare speech intelligibility and SRM between Western (non-tonal) and Mandarin Chinese (tonal) native-speaking listeners in speech-like maskers with various reverberant rooms using internationally comparable test materials.

Therefore, this study aims at systematically investigating the effect of reverberation and masker type on the speech intelligibility of tonal and non-tonal languages, considering scenarios where the maskers are either spatially separated from or co-located with the target speaker. Our main hypotheses are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Since pitch and TFS cues are crucial for understanding speech in Mandarin but less so in German, reverberation is expected to have a stronger impact on Mandarin speech if sound reflections impair pitch or TFS cues.

Hypothesis 2: If envelope modulation power of the Mandarin and German material is a reliable predictor of speech intelligibility, then the material with the highest modulation power should yield the best intelligibility. Otherwise, additional contributing cues may be missing, or the modeling concept for Mandarin may require refinements in comparison to non-tonal languages.

Hypothesis 3: Utilizing a vocoder to simulate CI speech processing and thus modified availability of TFS and AM cues, our hypothesis is that the current CI speech processors are expected to have a greater effect on the Mandarin CI users than on German CI users in anechoic conditions, especially concerning tone recognition. The effect of reverberation on Mandarin and German CI users might be similar due to the already deteriorated speech by the CI processing.

First, both native Mandarin-Chinese-speaking (CMNS; tonal) and German-speaking (GS; non-tonal) NH listeners were recruited and the speech recognition threshold (SRT) was measured using internationally comparable speech test materials developed according to the guidelines published by the International Collegium of Rehabilitative Audiology (Akeroyd *et al.*, 2015); the Mandarin-Chinese matrix test (CMNmatrix) (Hu *et al.*, 2018b), and the German matrix test (OLSA) (Wagner *et al.*, 1999), respectively. Both SRT and SRM were measured with stationary noise and fluctuating nonsense speech maskers in different reverberant rooms. In these critical conditions, maskers and reverberation interact in a synergistic manner to impair speech recognition. In other words, the influence of reverberation depends on the nature of the masker. For example, reverberation generally has a stronger effect on fluctuating maskers than on stationary maskers due to the loss of dip listening (e.g., Bib Berger and Ewert, 2019). To simulate natural binaural and spatial communication scenarios, a frontal target talker was employed, along with maskers placed either in a co-located position or symmetrically at $\pm 60^\circ$ angles (Best *et al.*, 2015; Lingner *et al.*, 2016; Ewert *et al.*, 2017; Hu *et al.*, 2018a). SRTs were determined with and without simulated CI processing, using headphone presentation in a sound attenuated booth. Such configurations were tested in three virtual rooms with different reverberation times (T60), using headphone auralization: anechoic, a small room with T60 of 0.6 s, and a large room with T60 of 3 s.

Second, an auditory-model based analysis was performed to analyze how reverberation affects pitch, spectral and AM cues, which are essential for understanding speech in both tonal and non-tonal languages. Following the concept of Jørgensen and Dau (2011), AM cues in this study are represented by the envelope-power calculated in modulation filters (Ewert and Dau, 2000). Differences in AM patterns between tonal and non-tonal languages may provide insights into which language is more affected by reverberation. Additionally, the effects of reverberation on pitch contours, pitch histograms, and frequency distribution and the output of an auditory Gammatone filterbank (Patterson *et al.*, 1987) will be assessed for tonal and non-tonal languages.

II. METHODS

A. Listeners

Twelve native GS NH listeners (five male, seven female) aged 22–29 years (mean 24.9 years) and 12 native

CMNS NH listeners (eight male, four female) aged 22–31 years (mean 26.2 years) participated in the experiments. All had audiometric thresholds of 20 dB HL or better at octave frequencies between 125 and 8 kHz. All GS participants were native German speakers with no prior experience to Mandarin. All CMNS participants were native Mandarin speakers and had German language skills ranging from A1 to A2 level according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages. This level indicates basic communication proficiency in German, ensuring that they could engage in fundamental interactions while maintaining their Mandarin as their primary language. All listeners were evaluated by a structured interview and questionnaires before the experiment to ensure linguistic and cultural alignment with the study's objectives. They were provided voluntary written informed consent, obtained with the approval of the Ethics Committee of the University of Oldenburg, following a full explanation of the experimental protocol. Listeners received an hourly compensation for their participation.

B. Stimuli

The target speech was the CMNmatrix test (Hu *et al.*, 2018b) for CMNS listeners and the female German OLSA (Wagner *et al.*, 1999; Ahrlich, 2013) for GS listeners. Both matrix sentence tests use a base matrix of 50 words containing five different categories (name-verb-number-adjective-object) with ten alternatives each. Sentences of a fixed syntactical structure are generated from the 50 words as a random walk across each category, e.g., “郭毅带走两个普通的灯笼 (Guoyi took away two ordinary lanterns)” and “Peter sieht sieben schwere Steine (Peter sees seven heavy stones)” from CMNmatrix and OLSA, respectively. Since these sentences are syntactically fixed but semantically unpredictable, they are difficult to memorize allowing for repeated measurements within the same listener. The matrix sentence test is a well-established psychometric curve-based method for SRT determination, which has demonstrated to be highly comparable across more than 20 languages (see Kollmeier *et al.*, 2015 for an extensive review). The sentences in the two matrix tests are spoken by two native female talkers, the reference SRTs for their corresponding speech-shaped noises (SSNs) in the open-set tests are -9.3 ± 0.8 dB for CMNmatrix test (Hu *et al.*, 2018b) and -9.3 ± 0.2 dB for the female German OLSA (Ahrlich, 2013), respectively. Two different masker types were used: (1) International female fluctuating masker (IFFM) (Holube *et al.*, 2010), which is non-sense speech composed of snippets of continuous speech uttered by six different female talkers in different languages (including German and Mandarin). (2) A stationary speech-shaped noise (SSN) derived from the IFFM stimulus by a fast Fourier transformation, randomization of the phases, and inverse fast Fourier transformation. The overall durations of the IFFM and the SSN were 55 and 60 s, respectively. From these signals, two randomized, statistically independent noise tokens, representing left and right

maskers, were extracted during the experiment. All maskers were normalized to the same long-term level.

Virtual acoustics and headphone auralization were used to render the spatial stimuli. The target and masker materials were convolved with binaural room impulse responses generated with the room acoustics simulator (RAZR) (Wendt *et al.*, 2014; Kirsch *et al.*, 2023; Ewert *et al.*, 2025). Three rooms (R1, R2, and R3) were considered in this study. R1 was an anechoic room and served as a reference without reverberation, only providing the direct sound of the target and maskers. R2 was a small reverberant room with the size of $7 \times 5 \times 3 \text{ m}^3$ (length \times width \times height) and a short reverberation time of $T60 = 0.6 \text{ s}$, which provides optimal acoustical quality in terms of speech intelligibility [see DIN18041, 2004, their Eq. (6)] as desirable for, e.g., a seminar room. R3 was a larger room with the size of $21 \times 15 \times 9 \text{ m}^3$ and $T60 = 3.0 \text{ s}$, representative for a large auditorium or church. In all rooms the height of the receiver, and the target and masker sources were 1.7 m above ground. The distances between target/masker sources to the receiver were 1.0 m for R1, R2 and 6.0 m for R3, respectively. The target was always located in front of the listener (0°). Two spatial configurations in the horizontal plane were tested in each room (R1, R2, and R3) for each masker (SSN and IFFM): (1) co-located with the target at 0° (coLoc); (2) symmetrically located at $\pm 60^\circ$ (symm). As shown in Biberger and Ewert (2019, their Fig. 1), the target-masker-receiver locations were positioned slightly off center and rotated in all rooms to avoid an unnatural, completely symmetrical location and orientation of the sources and receiver in the rooms.

In addition, for the anechoic room (R1), an artificial listening condition referred to as ILDinf was tested, where the acoustic crosstalk from the contralateral masker was removed and which thus provides optimal conditions for better-ear glimpsing. In the ILDinf configuration, the left and right channels of the 0° -binaural room impulse responses were used for the two different maskers in the respective ear. The ILDinf configuration was tested for two reasons: (1) to investigate the possible benefit of better-ear glimpsing for CMNS and GS listeners in optimal binaural configurations by enhancing the ILD cues; and (2) as a cross-validation of Hu *et al.* (2018a), where the same configuration as the anechoic room was used for simulated bilateral CI (BiCI; NH listener with bilaterally vocoded sounds), bilateral MED-EL CI users, and NH GS listeners using the male version of the German matrix test.

In total, there were two appointments for each subject in both groups: non-vocoded tests (first appointment) and vocoded tests (second appointment). Each appointment consisted of 14 test conditions as listed in Table I and took around 2 h/appointment including breaks.

Figure 1 presents some example waveforms and spectrograms for one CMN sentence (Guo1Yi4 Dai4zou3 Liang3ge4 Pu3tong1de0 Deng1long2 in PinYin) and one OLSA sentence (Peter sieht sieben schwere Steine) in the three different test rooms. The pitch contours (i.e., fundamental frequency F_0), indicated by black lines in the spectrograms of the anechoic room, were extracted using the STRAIGHT software package (Kawahara *et al.*, 2008). These contours represent variations in pitch over time, which is especially important for tonal languages, such as Mandarin.

Overall, Fig. 1 demonstrates that reverberation affects both the envelope waveform and the pitch contour of speech signals, with more pronounced effects as reverberation increases (from anechoic to small room to large room), especially for the CMN sentence. For instance, increased reverberation leads to greater smoothing and blending of amplitude variations as well as more blurred pitch contours and smeared frequencies.

C. Apparatus and procedure

SRTs were measured using both matrix sentence tests with the identical adaptive procedure (Brand and Kollmeier, 2002) to determine the SNR at which 50% of the presented words in a sentence were understood correctly. In this adaptive procedure, a generalization of Hagerman and Kinnefors (1995) is proposed which changes the presentation level of the subsequent sentence according to the discrimination value obtained in the previous sentence. The resulting psychometric curve, including slope and SRT (the SNR level corresponding to 50% speech perception accuracy), may provide a more comprehensive view of the relationship between speech perception and masker interference compared to selected SNR tests (e.g., Plomp and Mimpen, 1979). Measurements were performed as a closed test, i.e., the listeners were instructed to select the words via a touch screen and were allowed to guess, without feedback. The level of the masker was varied during the measurements while the level of the target sentences was fixed at 55 dB SPL. A list of 20 target sentences was used to measure the SRT in each masker condition. The order of presentation of

TABLE I. Summary of the 14 test conditions completed during each of the two appointments.^a

Masker types	IFFM and SSN							
	R1: anechoic room ^b			R2: small reverberant room; T60 = 0.6 s			R3: larger reverberant room; T60 = 3.0 s	
Room types	coLoc	symm	ILDinf	coLoc	symm	coLoc	symm	
Masker/target positions	coLoc	symm	ILDinf	coLoc	symm	coLoc	symm	

^aIn the first appointment, participants completed 14 test conditions using non-vocoded materials, while in the second appointment, the same 14 test conditions were completed using vocoded materials. coLoc, co-located with the target at 0° ; symm, target located at 0° and masker symmetrically located at $\pm 60^\circ$; ILDinf, an artificial listening condition, where the acoustic crosstalk from the contralateral masker was removed; SSN, derived from the IFFM stimulus.

^bThis setup is similar to Hu *et al.* (2018a), where male OLSA sentences and the SSN derived from the corresponding male OLSA sentences were used. In the current study, female OLSA sentences were used for GS listeners, and the same SSN generated from the IFFM was used for both language groups.

FIG. 1. Example waveforms and spectrograms of one CMN sentence (“Guo1Yi4 Dai4zou3 Liang3ge4 Pu3tong1de0 Deng1long2” in PinYin, Guo Yi took away two ordinary lanterns, rows 1 and 2) and one OLSA sentence (“Peter sieht sieben schwere Steine,” Peter sees seven heavy stones, rows 3 and 4) in anechoic (R1), small (R2), and large (R3) reverberant rooms. Dashed black vertical lines indicate the boundaries between the five elements of the Matrix sentence.

the room conditions was Latin-Square balanced, while the order of the within-room conditions (masker type, masker position) was randomized. To familiarize with the speech material and task, one list of 20 sentences was presented prior to the actual measurements in both the vocoded and non-vocoded tests. The masker in the training setup was collocated with the speech at 0°, using the corresponding CMNmatrix noise (Hu *et al.*, 2018b) and female OLSA noise (Wagener *et al.*, 1999; Ahrlich, 2013), respectively. All the stimuli were presented binaurally via Sennheiser HD 650 headphones that were calibrated with a Bruel&Kjaer artificial ear 4153, type 3142 microphone and type 2669 pre-amplifier. The measurements took place in a double-walled, sound-attenuating booth. The sampling frequency of the stimuli was 44.1 kHz. The AFC framework for MATLAB (Ewert, 2013) was used to perform the speech tests.

D. Vocoder CI simulations

In the simulated BiCI experiment (NH listeners presented with vocoded speech), the same bilateral vocoder as used in Hu *et al.* (2018a) was applied. Hu *et al.* (2018a) showed that their bilateral vocoder can partially replicate the SRT and SRM performance of real BiCI listeners. This vocoder, originally extended from Bräcker *et al.* (2009), has been further developed within an open source CI simulation framework (Hu *et al.*, 2022b; Hu *et al.*, 2023). It includes most key signal processing principles of current CIs.

Briefly, a basic continuous interleaved sampling (CIS) strategy (Wilson *et al.*, 1991) was implemented to simulate the processing from acoustic signal to electric signal: A 12-channel, third-order Gammatone filterbank with center frequencies between 120 Hz and 7410 Hz was used. The envelope of each channel was then extracted and processed as follows: frequency weighted according to previous studies (e.g., Nogueira *et al.*, 2005; Hu *et al.*, 2015; Hu *et al.*, 2018a), low-pass filtered (with a cutoff-frequency of 200 Hz), sampled at the CI stimulation rate of 800 pulses per second, and compressed with a nonlinear logarithmic loudness-growth-function (LGF).

In the vocoder synthesis, the timing of the envelope sampling across channels within a time frame was randomized to avoid a possible unpleasant pitch percept introduced by sequential stimulation. After this “pulsatile” sampling, spatial spread of the electric field in the perilymph was simulated by multiplying each pulse at a given time with a two-sided exponentially decaying function across channels (thus in the frequency domain) to transfer stimulation to adjacent channels. Then the signal of each channel was filtered using a third-order one-ERB-wide synthesis Gammatone filter bank with the same center frequencies as in the analysis filter bank. Finally, the frequency channels were summed to create an audio signal. The root mean square (RMS) of the vocoders (broadband) output was scaled to the same RMS as the input signal in order to compensate for level changes

caused by pulsatile sampling and/or bandpass filtering. Binaural synchronization between the random pulses was achieved by using the identical (random) pulse sequence in both ears, modulated with the individual envelopes in each ear.

E. Speech cue analysis

An auditory-model-based acoustic analysis was performed on the OLSA and CMN sentences used in the measurements to investigate the differences in potential speech cues (e.g., F0 and energy distribution across frequency bands) and their changes with reverberation between Mandarin and German sentences. For the analysis, 55 s of speech material was used, which was generated by concatenating randomly selected matrix sentences. The duration of the IFFM masker used in the analysis was about 60 s.

1. AM

To assess the effect of room reverberation on AMs of OLSA and CMN sentences, an analysis similar to the speech intelligibility models of (Jørgensen and Dau, 2011; Bib Berger and Ewert, 2016) was used.

The speech signals were processed by a Gammatone filterbank (same settings as used for spectral cue analysis, with a frequency range between 500 to 5 kHz) followed by Hilbert envelope extraction and low-pass filtering (first-order, cut-off frequency of 150 Hz). The low-pass filtered envelopes were processed by a modulation filterbank consisting of a third-order low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of 1 Hz and bandpass filters ranging from 2 to 64 Hz with a Q value of 1. For each of the modulation filterbank outputs, the envelope power, normalized by the DC-power of the corresponding auditory channel, was calculated. In order to reflect limitations in human sensitivity to AM (Viemeister, 1979; Kohlrausch *et al.*, 2000), a lower limit of -27 dB was applied for the (normalized) envelope power.

2. Spectral cues

For spectral cues, the same signal processing steps described above for the AM cues were used to obtain the low-pass filtered envelopes in each of the 22 auditory channels, ranging from 63 Hz to 8 kHz.

3. Pitch

The fundamental frequency was estimated using the STRAIGHT algorithm by Kawahara *et al.* (2008), which is widely used in the speech research community. The MATLAB implementation of the algorithm was applied with default parameters, where pitch information was estimated every 1 ms for frequencies ranging from 40 to 800 Hz using an analysis window of 80 ms. The same parameters were used for all stimuli and across all considered conditions, for both voiced and unvoiced speech segments.

F. Data analysis

SRM was derived by subtracting the SRTs of the spatially separated conditions from the corresponding co-located conditions. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (version 25, IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). To assess the effect of different test conditions on SRTs or SRM in different subject groups, several mixed-design analyses of variance (mdANOVA) were performed. Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied whenever the sphericity assumption was found to be violated. Pairwise *post hoc* comparisons t-tests using Bonferroni correction were performed in some cases to gain more insight into the nature of the effects. Bonferroni adjusted p-values are reported as provided by SPSS. Unless explicitly stated in the text, the number of comparisons used for the adjustment by SPSS is the number of possible pairwise comparisons for the assessed factor (i.e., for a factor with two levels, no correction was applied; for the factors with three levels, the p-values were multiplied by three in the adjustment).

A *post hoc* power analysis was conducted using G*Power (Faul *et al.*, 2009) to evaluate the probability of detecting true effects with the current sample size. Unless explicitly stated, the statistical power for conditions showing significant results exceeded 0.8, indicating adequate power. Power values were not reported for conditions where no significant differences were observed.

III. RESULTS

A. Speech perception

Figure 2 shows the mean SRTs (left column) and SRM (right column) along with the inter-individual standard deviations for the non-vocoded (upper panels) and vocoded (lower panels) tests for CMNS and GS listeners. For SRT, the dashed lines [Figs. 2(a) and 2(c)] connect all co-located conditions, while for SRM [Figs. 2(b) and 2(d)] they connect symm conditions with IFFM, across different rooms. The relative steepness (or slopes) of these lines illustrates the effect of reverberation changes on SRT and SRM: (1) SRTs increase with increasing reverberation. (2) There are detrimental effects of CI processing on speech intelligibility, i.e., increased SRTs and reduced SRM in the vocoded conditions [Figs. 2(c) and 2(d)] compared to the non-vocoded conditions [Figs. 2(a) and 2(b)]. (3) The benefit from spatial separation, the SRM, decreases with increasing reverberation in most non-vocoded conditions, but not in vocoded conditions.

For all SRT values shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(c), a five-way mdANOVA was conducted with factors: group, vocoder, masker, position (coLoc, symm), and room (R1, R2, R3). The analysis revealed that all main effects were highly significant ($p < 0.001$). The average SRTs were significantly lower for CMNS listeners compared to GS listeners, [$F(1, 20) = 16.01$, $p = 0.001$]. Most two-way interactions were also significant ($p < 0.005$), with the exception of interactions between

FIG. 2. Average SRT (a), (c) and SRM (b), (d) for the non-vocoded [NH listeners: (a), (b)] and vocoded [simulated BiCI users: (c), (d)] tests for CMNS (filled symbols: black and gray) and GS listeners (open symbols: dark and light red). The masker positions are indicated on the x axis and marked with different rectangular backgrounds (green: coLoc; blue: symm; red: ILDinf). Different symbols represent different masker types (triangle: IFFM; rectangle: SSN). (a), (c) Dashed lines connect all SRT50 values under the co-located condition. (b), (d) Dashed lines connect SRM values under symm conditions with IFFM. Vertical dotted lines separate the results for different rooms, labeled as R1, R2, and R3 in each subplot. Dotted horizontal lines in (b), (d) indicate no SRM. coLoc, co-located with the target at 0°; symm, target located at 0° and masker symmetrically located at ±60°; ILDinf, an artificial listening condition, where the acoustic crosstalk from the contralateral masker was removed.

group × room, group × vocoder, group × location, and room × location.

For the SRM values presented in Figs. 2(b) and 2(d), a four-way mdANOVA (group, vocoder, masker, and room) revealed significant main effects ($p < 0.001$) of vocoder and masker. No overall significant group differences in SRM were observed. Additionally, significant two-way interactions were found for vocoder × room, vocoder × masker, and room × masker (all $p < 0.005$).

It is worth noting that, based on an observed effect size of 2.2 and a sample size of 12 participants per group in the anechoic room (as in both the current study and Hu *et al.*, 2018a), the power analysis revealed a very high statistical power of 0.9998, indicating that the study was well powered to detect group differences. However, while the current sample size provided strong power for most observed effects, increasing the sample size would further improve the reliability of the findings, particularly in conditions where no significant differences were observed, and increase confidence in detecting potential effects in those cases.

In the following subsections, we present detailed comparisons between CMNS and GS groups with respect to masker type, room type (amount of reverberation), and the impact of CI processing, under either non-vocoded (NH) or vocoded (simulated CI) listening conditions. This approach reduces the number of factors in the mdANOVA analysis,

thereby lowering the complexity of the model and facilitating clearer interpretation of the results.

1. Anechoic room conditions

Figure 2 shows the detrimental effects of CI processing on speech intelligibility: (1) increased SRTs and reduced SRM in the vocoded conditions compared to the non-vocoded conditions for both groups. (2) Both language groups greatly benefit from spatial separation and ILDinf for the non-vocoded signals. However, no binaural advantage is observed in noise vocoder simulated BiCI listeners for the ±60° spatial configuration (please refer to Hu *et al.*, 2018a for more details).

For the non-vocoded conditions in the anechoic room (R1), a three-way mdANOVA of SRTs [factors: group (CMNS, GS), masker (IFFM, SSN), and position (coLoc, symm, ILDinf)] showed a significant main effect of most factors and their interactions with statistical power values above 0.89, except position × group interaction. The CMNS group shows overall lower (~4.5 dB) SRTs than the GS group [$F(1, 20) = 44.55, p < 0.001, \text{power} > 0.999$]. The SRT difference between the two groups is larger for IFFM than for SSN, about 3.3 dB ($p < 0.001$) for SSN and is even larger (~5.7 dB, $p < 0.001$) for IFFM. A three-way ANOVA of SRM [factors: group, masker, position (symm, ILDinf)]

showed a significant main effect of most factors and their interactions (with power values from 0.75 to >0.999), except position \times group and masker \times group. There is no significant SRM difference between the two groups.

Similar to the non-vocoded conditions, the simulated CMNS BiCI group shows significantly lower SRTs (~ 2 dB smaller) than the GS counterpart [$F(1, 20) = 10.37$, $p < 0.005$, power = 0.88]. *Post hoc* pairwise comparison shows CMNS BiCI listeners, on average, have significantly better SRTs than GS listeners in SSN (~ 2.2 dB smaller, $p = 0.001$, power > 0.999) and in IFFM (~ 1.7 dB smaller, $p < 0.05$, power = 0.7). Consistent with Hu *et al.* (2018a), the SRTs with SSN are significantly lower (~ 5 dB) than with IFFM ($p < 0.001$, power > 0.999), contrary to the non-vocoded conditions. There are no significant SRM differences between the two simulated BiCI groups.

The SRT differences between simulated CMNS and GS BiCI users are smaller than those between the CMNS and GS listeners in the non-vocoded conditions, especially for the IFFM.

2. All room conditions

For the non-vocoded conditions, in the presence of maskers and reverberation (R2 vs R1, and R3 vs R1), Fig. 2(a) (excluding ILDinf conditions) shows that, for both CMNS and GS groups, SRTs increase with increasing reverberation. A four-way mdANOVA of SRTs [factors: group (CMNS, GS), masker (IFFM, SSN), room (R1, R2, R3), and position (coLoc, symm)] showed a significant main effect of all factors ($p < 0.001$) and most two-way interactions (at least $p < 0.05$), except group \times location.

The CMNS group exhibits significantly lower mean SRTs (-12.7 dB) compared to the GS group (-8.8 dB). *Post hoc* pairwise comparisons reveal a significant SRT difference between the two groups (for both SSN and IFFM, in all three rooms; at least $p < 0.05$). Notably, the SRT difference between reverberant and anechoic conditions is more pronounced with IFFM than with SSN in both groups, especially for strong reverberation.

For co-located situations, speech intelligibility differences evoked by different amounts of reverberation (represented by R1, R2, and R3) are shown by dashed lines in Fig. 2(a) for GS and CMNS groups and for both masker types. The slopes of the black and the dark red dashed lines (SSN) are shallower than the slopes of the gray and light red lines (IFFM), especially between R2 and R3, which suggests that reverberation has a more substantial impact on SRTs with the speech-like masker than with stationary noise. Figure 2(a) also demonstrates that the impact of increasing reverberation on the SRTs is nonlinear, as indicated by the varying slopes between R1 and R2, R2 and R3, and R1 and R3. Both the more nonlinear and larger effect of reverberation with IFFM relative to SSN could explain the crossing of the black and gray dashed lines, as well as the crossing of the dark and light red dashed lines in Fig. 2(a). Specifically, SRTs are lower with IFFM than with SSN in the anechoic room

(R1), but higher with IFFM than with SSN in the large reverberant room (R3) for both groups.

Moreover, when comparing the two language groups (CMNS vs GS) in SSN [Fig. 2(a): black vs dark red dashed lines] and in IFFM [Fig. 2(a): gray vs light red dashed lines], the effect of increasing reverberation is similar for both groups in SSN. However, in IFFM, the CMNS group experiences a larger effect, particularly as reverberation increases. These results suggest that the effect of reverberation (R1, R2, and R3) on SRTs and SRM is nonlinear and depends on language group, masker type, and spatial configuration.

It is important to note that the differences in speech intelligibility caused by different amounts of reverberation (represented by R1, R2, and R3) in the symmetrically located maskers were comparable between two language groups. Therefore, dashed lines were omitted in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) to maintain a clear and uncluttered presentation.

A three-way mdANOVA of SRM [factors: group (CMNS, GS), masker (IFFM, SSN), room (R1, R2, R3)] showed significant main effects ($p < 0.001$) of room and masker as well as the two-way interactions group \times room ($p < 0.05$), and masker \times room ($p < 0.001$). Despite the CMNS group having lower SRTs, *post hoc* pairwise comparison showed no significant differences between the two groups for SRM [Fig. 2(b), excluding ILDinf conditions]. However, CMNS showed smaller SRM in R2, but larger SRM in R3 than GS listeners for IFFM ($p < 0.05$).

The SRM in the anechoic room R1 is significantly larger than in the two reverberant rooms ($p < 0.001$), while there are no significant SRM differences between R2 and R3 for both groups. However, CMNS and GS groups exhibit different decreasing patterns across rooms for the IFFM (e.g., average SRM: CMNS, R1/R2/R3, 5.4/3.0/3.2 dB; GS, 7.8/4.5/2.3 dB). The SRM significantly decreased with increasing reverberation ($p < 0.005$) for GS listeners, but only show a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) from R1 to R2 for the CMNS listeners.

Interestingly, when examining the gray and light red dashed lines (IFFM) in Fig. 2(b), a saturation effect appears to occur in the small reverberant room (R2) for CMNS listeners, where further increases in reverberation do not significantly change the SRM. In other words, the SRM of CMNS listeners may already be impaired with a smaller amount of reverberation, as present in a seminar room (R2). This pattern differs from the GS group, which shows a continued decrease in SRM with increasing reverberation (R3).

For the vocoded conditions, as in the non-vocoded case, increasing reverberation leads to higher SRTs [Fig. 2(c), excluding ILDinf conditions]. In contrast to the non-vocoded case, the average SRTs in SSN are ~ 5 dB lower than in IFFM. A four-way mdANOVA of SRTs [factors: group (CMNS, GS), masker (IFFM, SSN), room (R1, R2, R3), and position (coLoc, symm)] showed a significant main effect of room, masker ($p < 0.001$), and a room \times masker interaction ($p < 0.05$). No significant group difference was found, although the CMNS group showed ~ 2 dB lower averaged SRTs. Pairwise comparisons indicated

significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) SRTs for CMNS in R1 (except co-located SSN) and in R2 for symmetrical IFFM. This suggests a stronger effect of CI processing on Mandarin compared to German, as the significant group differences (CMNS has lower SRTs than GS) seen in non-vocoded tests disappeared under vocoded conditions. Furthermore, it also suggests that reverberation may affect CMNS BiCI users more than GS users, given that CMNS listeners had lower SRTs in R1 but no significant difference was observed between the two groups in R2 and R3.

For SRM [Fig. 2(d), excluding ILDinf], no significant main effects or interactions were found, and no significant difference between the two simulated BiCI groups was observed, likely due to the absence of SRM in symmetrical masker conditions.

3. Differences between rooms

To examine the effect of reverberation on speech intelligibility, the relative performance (SRTs and SRM) across rooms with varying reverberation time was further analyzed. Figure 3 shows the Δ SRT and Δ SRM between small reverberant and anechoic rooms (R2-R1), between large and small reverberant rooms (R3-R2), and between large reverberant and anechoic rooms (R3-R1).

For the non-vocoded conditions, a four-way mdANOVA of Δ SRTs [factors: group (CMNS, GS), masker (IFFM, SSN), room difference (R2-R1, R3-R2, R3-R1), and position (coLoc, symm)] showed a significant main effect of all factors

($p < 0.001$) and most two-way interactions (at least $p < 0.05$), except group \times masker, and group \times matrix. A three-way mdANOVA of Δ SRM (group, masker, and room difference) showed significant main effects of all factors ($p < 0.001$) and the two-way interaction room \times masker ($p < 0.005$).

Figure 3(a) clearly shows that the Δ SRT_{R2-R1} in the symmetrically positioned maskers (symm) is very similar between two language groups, suggesting that reverberation has a comparable impact on binaural cues in both groups.

For co-located IFFM, the SRT differences Δ SRT_{R2-R1} [Fig. 3(a)] do not show any significant differences between two groups [consistent with Fig. 2(a), parallel light-red and gray dashed lines between R1 and R2 indicate similar slopes], although CMNS listeners showed a slightly larger Δ SRT_{R2-R1}. However, stronger reverberation (T60 = 3 s, R3-R2, and R3-R1) induces larger Δ SRT for the co-located IFFM [Fig. 3(a) (steeper slope, faster SRT increase in Fig. 2(a))] in the CMNS group than the GS group: Δ SRT_{R3-R2} (~2.4 dB, $p < 0.05$) and Δ SRT_{R3-R1} (~3.3 dB, $p = 0.01$), indicating that strong reverberation had a more detrimental effect on understanding speech in the presence of co-located IFFM for the CMNS than for the GS listeners.

Although both groups show similar Δ SRM for IFFM in room with mild reverberation (R2, e.g., a daily seminar room with optimal acoustical quality), stronger reverberation (R3, e.g., in a large auditorium or church), further decreases the SRM for GS listeners but not for CMNS listeners. For example, CMNS listeners exhibit a plateau with

FIG. 3. Average Δ SRT (a, c) and Δ SRM (b, d) for the non-vocoded (a, b) and vocoded (c, d) tests from CMNS (black) and GS listeners (red). Different color bars represent different masker types as indicated in the legend. The room differences are separated by vertical dotted lines and are indicated with R2-R1, R3-R2, and R3-R1 in each subplot, respectively. The Δ SRT and Δ SRM in dB are shown on the y axis. The masker positions are indicated on the x axis and are color coded as in Fig. 2. Different colors represent different masker types, as indicated in the legend. Δ SRT, speech reception thresholds differences between two rooms; Δ SRM, SRM differences between two rooms; coLoc, co-located with the target at 0°; symm, target located at 0° and masker symmetrically located at $\pm 60^\circ$; SSN, derived from the IFFM stimulus.

similar SRM in R3 and R2 [Fig. 2(b)], i.e., a near zero Δ SRM [Fig. 3(b)]. However, *post hoc* pairwise comparison showed that Δ SRM is significantly larger in GS listeners compared to CMNS listeners for R3-R2 (~ 2.4 dB, $p < 0.005$), and R3-R1 (~ 3.3 dB, $p < 0.05$) with IFFM.

B. Speech cue analysis

1. AM

The nine panels at the right side of Fig. 4 show the AM spectra from auditory filters with center frequencies ranging from 200 Hz and 5 kHz. In each panel, the long-term integrated envelope power is plotted as a function of the center frequency of the modulation filter shown in the x axis. The AM spectra of CMN and OLSA sentences are shown in black and red lines. Solid, dotted, and dashed lines indicate anechoic (R1), small reverberant (R2), and the large reverberant (R3) room, respectively. Most of the panels clearly show higher envelope power for OLSA sentences than for CMN, implying a larger AM depth (i.e., higher amplitude variations over time) in OLSA than in CMN sentences. In the range from 1 to 16 Hz, the pattern for the OLSA sentences in the anechoic room resembles the classical modulation spectra of speech (Houtgast and Steeneken, 1985). A peak around 4 Hz is clearly visible, corresponding roughly to the syllable rate. However, this peak is less pronounced for the CMN sentences. In addition, CMN sentences show higher modulation energy ratio between frequency below and above 2 kHz compared to the OLSA sentences. Overall, increased reverberation, particularly in room R3 with a T60 of 3 s, leads to a low-pass-like envelope power pattern for both OLSA and CMN sentences. It is important to note that

reverberation had a stronger impact on AMs of OLSA than CMN sentences, which is represented by mean envelope power differences between rooms R1 and R2. They are about 1.5 and 1 dB for OLSA and CMN sentences, respectively. Similarly, larger mean envelope power differences between R1 and R3 were observed for OLSA (4.5 dB) than for CMN (3.6 dB).

2. Spectral cues

The left panels in Fig. 4 illustrates that reverberation affects the frequency spectra of CMN and OLSA sentences. For instance, the frequency spectra show a broad peak across frequencies approximately from 200 Hz to 3 kHz, and the high-frequency content (>3 kHz) diminishes significantly in the large room (red dashed line). However, these effects are slightly more pronounced in CMN than in the OLSA sentences.

3. Pitch

Figure 1 illustrates the differences in the effect of reverberation on one CMN and one OLSA sentence, concerning the envelope and pitch contour. To gain a deeper understanding, Fig. 5 shows the distribution of pitch contours (pitch histograms) for 55 s CMN [Figs. 5(a), 5(d), and 5(g)], female OLSA [Figs. 5(b), 5(e), and 5(h)], target speech material, and 60 s IFFM [Figs. 5(c), 5(f), and 5(g)] in the three rooms. For the IFFM, the F0 was directly extracted from the IFFM signal, including six speakers from six different languages (Arabic, English, French, German, Mandarin, and Spanish) with fundamental frequencies ranging from 194 to 208 Hz (see Holube *et al.*, 2010, their Table

FIG. 4. The left panel shows the frequency spectra of CMN (top) and OLSA (bottom) sentences in anechoic (solid black lines), small reverberant (solid red lines), and large reverberant (dashed red lines) rooms. The right panel displays the AM spectra for the outputs of nine auditory filters with center frequencies ranging from 200 Hz and 5 kHz. Each point represents the long-term integrated envelope power at the output of a modulation filter (Jørgensen and Dau, 2011; Jørgensen *et al.*, 2013), plotted as a function of its center frequency (f_c), for CMN (black) and OLSA (dark red) sentences in anechoic (solid lines), small reverberant (dotted lines), and large reverberant (dashed lines) rooms.

FIG. 5. Pitch histograms of CMN [column 1: (a), (d), (g)], female OLSA [column 2: (b), (e), (h)] sentences, and IFFM [column 3: (c), (f), (i)] in three different rooms: anechoic [R1; row 1: (a), (b), (c)], small [R2; row 2: (d), (e), (f)], and large [R3; row 3: (g), (h), (i)] reverberant rooms. The histogram was generated using MATLAB with equally spaced frequency bins of 5-Hz width each, spanning the range of 100–400 Hz.

I). The processing scheme for F0 extraction was identical for all three speech signals. Figures 5(a)–5(c) show a similar pitch distribution for German OLSA sentences and IFFM in anechoic, with a distinct peak between 170 and 180 Hz. Such peak (but less distinct), at about 150 Hz was also observed in the pitch histogram of the CMN sentences. However, it shows higher pitch variability, represented by larger values in the frequency range between 250 and 350 Hz, than those observed in both OLSA and IFFM materials. This is consistent with previous studies suggesting that the frequency band importance function of Mandarin speech has greater values in the lower frequencies compared to English because Chinese listeners rely more on pitch changes in the lower-frequency vowels (e.g., Chen *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2016). Figure 5 clearly shows that reverberation has a greater impact on CMN sentences compared to female OLSA sentences and IFFM, particularly under high reverberation conditions (lower row, large room R3). Additionally, reverberation appears to alter the shape of the histogram differently for CMN sentences, female OLSA sentences, and IFFM. For example, the dominance of low-frequency pitches around 150 Hz in the histogram gradually diminishes with increasing reverberation. However, it should be noted that the results depend on the accuracy of the pitch extraction algorithm. Although the pitch contours extracted using the STRAIGHT software package (Kawahara

et al., 2008) showed reasonable results in the anechoic room as shown in Fig. 1, the performance in reverberant conditions, especially in the large reverberant room, needs further validation.

IV. DISCUSSION

In general, SRTs increase with increasing reverberation, particularly in the case of fluctuating IFFM. Previous studies suggested that this increase is mainly attributed to the reduction of AMs in the masker and target signals (Houtgast *et al.*, 1980; Lavandier and Culling, 2008; see data in Jørgensen *et al.*, 2013). Nevertheless, both groups still benefit from spatial separation of target and masker sounds compared to co-located configurations. However, no binaural advantage is observed in noise vocoder simulated BiCI listeners for the $\pm 60^\circ$ spatial configuration.

A. Effect of maskers in the anechoic room (R1)

Overall, the findings in the anechoic room (R1) align with similar conditions outlined in Hu *et al.* (2018a) who showed that both simulated and MED-EL bilateral CI users exhibited a significantly reduced better-ear glimpsing and diminished SRM compared to NH listeners, in agreement with previous CI studies (Schleich *et al.*, 2004; Misurelli

and Litovsky, 2012; Dorman *et al.*, 2014). In addition, the enlarged ILD (ILDinf) significantly improved the better-ear glimpsing performance in both simulated and MED-EL bilateral CI groups, but not in the NH group.

The current study further confirms that CI processing has detrimental effects on speech intelligibility in both languages. However, both groups greatly benefit from spatial separation and ILDinf for the non-vocoded natural signals. The mean SRM was smaller for the SSN than for IFFM in both symmetrically located maskers and ILDinf conditions for NH listeners. These findings align with previous studies using a similar or comparable setup (Ewert *et al.*, 2017; Hu *et al.*, 2018a; Biberger and Ewert, 2019) and can be explained by the availability of temporal gaps in the speech-like interferers, which enable more effective better-ear glimpsing than the SSN interferer. No binaural advantage is observed in noise vocoder simulated BiCI listeners for the $\pm 60^\circ$ spatial configuration.

As a possible consequence of dip listening (e.g., Festen and Plomp, 1990; Festen, 1993; Lorenzi *et al.*, 2006; Schubotz *et al.*, 2016), SRTs for IFFM are always lower, and the variability is larger compared to SSN, which is consistent with the following: Schubotz *et al.* (2016); Hu *et al.* (2018a); and Biberger and Ewert (2019). The use of additional acoustic cues, such as pitch in Mandarin speaking listeners, to aid dip listening might also partially explain the overall lower (~ 4.5 dB) SRTs in the CMNS group compared to the GS group especially for IFFM. However, it should be noted that the IFFM used in this study is based on six different languages, including Arabic, English, Mandarin, and Spanish (the four most spoken languages) along with French and German. It consists of a blend of sentences spoken by female speakers in each language and resembles normal speech but is unintelligible. Thus, although other languages known by the listeners have been shown to influence word recognition in babble (e.g., Gautreau *et al.*, 2013, 2015), such an effect with the IFFM is likely negligible, especially in terms of the role of informational masking, as discussed in previous studies with speech maskers (Brungart, 2001; Best *et al.*, 2015; Ewert *et al.*, 2017).

However, since five of six languages are non-tonal, the pitch distribution of the IFFM is indeed closer to German sentences than to Mandarin ones, as shown in Fig. 5. This might result in a greater masking effect in German listeners compared to the Chinese group. If available, a more balanced, international, speech-like IFFM masker incorporating an equal mix of tonal and non-tonal languages is recommended for future studies.

Additionally, cautions should be taken when comparing absolute SRTs between the GS and CMNS groups, as these differences may result from variations in the target sentences and maskers, or from speaker-related factors, such as individual vocal characteristics. Differences in SRT between different tests or languages are strongly influenced by the respective talker. As shown by Hochmuth *et al.* (2015), SRTs measured with matrix tests recorded by different talkers in the same language can vary by 3–5 dB between easily

understandable speakers and those who are more difficult to understand. For instance, the speaker in the CMN sentences was a well-trained professional TV broadcaster. Therefore, the speaker effect has to be accounted for when comparing reference values of different tests and languages, as it typically has a greater impact than language differences. The speaker effect was also observed in the recent studies based on CMNmatrix sentence recordings from 11 native Chinese-Mandarin talkers (six female and five male) (Hu *et al.*, 2022c; Chen *et al.*, 2025). Consequently, most of the conclusions regarding group differences in this study were based on relative values.

The simulated CMNS BiCI group shows significantly lower SRTs (~ 2 dB smaller) than the GS counterpart. However, the SRT differences between two simulated BiCI groups are smaller than the corresponding non-vocoded conditions, especially for the IFFM. This implies that CI processing could have more deleterious effects on the SRTs in Mandarin-speaking listeners relative to that in German-speaking ones, especially for IFFM, which agrees to the findings in Hu and Ewert (2021). One possible explanation is that the current CI processing failed to deliver some potential cues, such as fine structure, that Mandarin-speaking listeners rely on in natural hearing. Negative SRM was also reported in Hu *et al.* (2018a) for their German-speaking BiCI users and in Biberger and Ewert (2019) for diotic, long-term better-ear stimuli in GS NH listeners. The negative SRM values are expected to be a consequence of spectral masking because the level of SSN maskers convolved with the HRTF of the spatially separated masker position is slightly higher than the level of the SSN maskers convolved with the co-located HRTF.

In non-vocoded anechoic conditions, both CMNS and GS listeners could take advantage from “listen into dips,” as represented by lower SRTs for co-located fluctuating IFFM than for stationary SSN. However, this (monaural) dip listening observed in NH listeners appears to be hindered in simulated BiCI listeners. The observed deficit may be related to limitations of current CI-coding techniques. For instance, the limited spectro-temporal resolution in the current CI-coding strategy, due to the use of only 12 relatively broad channels and the transmission of only envelope information (please refer to Hu *et al.*, 2018a for more details). Previous studies (e.g., Gnansia *et al.*, 2008; Hopkins *et al.*, 2008) have shown that the ability to “listen into dips” may depend on TFS information, which helps to signal the presence of target speech in situations with interfering sounds. In this regard, the absence of TFS information in the vocoded conditions might be the reason why listeners were not able to benefit from the “dips.”

The positive SRM values shown in R1 [anechoic room, Fig. 2(b)] indicate that both listener groups in anechoic and non-vocoded conditions took advantage from spatially separating the target and the masker sources. However, although German-speaking listeners exhibited larger SRM in IFFM, there is no significant overall SRM difference between the two language groups for both NH and simulated BiCI

listeners. A larger sample size might increase confidence in detecting potential effects in this case.

B. Effect of maskers in reverberation

The SRT differences between IFFM and SSN in anechoic room (R1) were reduced or even reversed with increasing reverberation time (R2, R3). Additionally, SRTs are lower with IFFM than with SSN in the anechoic room (R1), but higher with IFFM than with SSN in the large reverberant room (R3) for both groups. These results suggest that the impact of reverberation on SRTs and SRM is nonlinear and depends on factors, such as the test material, masker type, spatial configuration, and reverberation time. The nonlinear impact of reverberation on the SRT observed in this study [Fig. 2(a)] aligns with the findings of [Biberger and Ewert \(2019\)](#).

The SRT difference between reverberant and anechoic conditions is more pronounced with IFFM than with SSN in both groups. Comparing SRTs for IFFM and SSN in co-located conditions [Fig. 2(a), coLoc] suggests that reverberation has a more substantial impact on SRTs with fluctuating speech-like maskers than with stationary noise, possibly due to the reduction of dip listening in reverberation. [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#) found that intelligibility first suffers due to the effect of the reverberation on the masker, which suggests that the more pronounced reduction of SRTs in IFFM compared to SSN in the co-located configurations in the less reverberant room (R2) may primarily result from flattened masker fluctuations. A similar effect was reported by [George et al. \(2008\)](#), where masking release disappeared for masker-dependent reverberation times between 0.25 and 1.0 s in a diffuse field under monaural conditions. Thus, the more pronounced or reversed SRT differences between IFFM and SSN in anechoic versus reverberant conditions may primarily result from reduced dip listening in the small reverberant room (R2) due to decreased IFFM masker fluctuation, as well as the diminished target speech modulations in the larger reverberant room (R3). In addition, the greater detrimental effect of the longer reverberation time in R3 on Mandarin-speaking listeners in co-located configurations compared to German-speaking listeners may be due to its additional impact on other important acoustic cues in the Mandarin sentences, such as pitch cues.

Interestingly, a saturation effect appears to occur in SRM in the small reverberant room (R2) for CMNS listeners, while the GS group shows a continued decrease in SRM with increasing reverberation (R3). One might wonder what drives such differences and whether these group-dependent SRT differences can be attributed more to the co-located (coLoc) or the separated (symm) condition. A comparison of SRT differences between CMNS and GS data for the symm IFFM conditions in R1, R2, and R3 [Fig. 2(a)] shows a rather constant difference of about 4 dB. However, the coLoc condition reveals that differences decrease with increasing reverberation. Thus, it is worthwhile to examine

the extent of reverberation on speech intelligibility, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3(a) suggests that mild reverberation affects both groups similarly (non-significant differences in $\Delta\text{SRT}_{\text{R2-R1}}$), further supporting the above assumption that degraded SRTs under co-located IFFM in the small reverberant room primarily result from reduced dip listening due to decreased IFFM masker fluctuation, consistent with [George et al. \(2008\)](#) and [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#). Since CMNS listeners showed a slightly larger $\Delta\text{SRT}_{\text{R2-R1}}$ (non-significant), a larger sample size might help in detect potential differences. However, we would expect the effect of mild reverberation on SRTs to be similar across both language groups, if not more severe for CMNS listeners. This is in contrast to [Kang \(1998\)](#), who found that the decrease in word intelligibility caused by reverberation was larger in English than in Mandarin. The differences to the current study could be due to the nonlinear impacts of reverberation and its dependence on multiple factors, such as the test material, masker type, spatial configuration, and reverberation time. For example, [Kang \(1998\)](#) compared the speech intelligibility at a fixed SNR with ambient noise (white noise), and the reverberant rooms tested in that study had a limited early decay time range of 0.6–1.3 s at 0.5–1 kHz.

It should be noted that the larger decrease in SRM in the German-speaking group compared to the Mandarin-speaking group is not due to differences in the impact of reverberation on SRTs in spatially separated conditions but rather in co-located conditions. As shown in Fig. 3(a), although reverberation affects both groups similarly in spatially separated conditions (symm), stronger reverberation (R3-R2, and R3-R1) has a greater impact on co-located SRTs in CMNS listeners but a larger effect on SRM in GS listeners for IFFM. This may result from diminished target speech modulations in the larger reverberant room (R3) and the impact of reverberation on other important acoustic cues, such as TFS and pitch cues. Thus, it could be speculated that if SRTs in co-located conditions were equivalent for both CMNS and GS listeners, reverberation should have a similar effect on both CMNS and GS listeners.

Briefly, for the non-vocoded speech, it appears that rooms with moderate to strong reverberation (e.g., large auditorium, church) make it more difficult for the CMNS than the GS listeners to separate the target sentence from the co-located IFFM maskers (steeper slopes between R3-R1 for CMNS than for GS), while both listener groups showed a similar performance in the mild reverberant room (R2, representing e.g., a typical seminar room). It is known that in situations where spatial cues are not available (e.g., coLoc condition), pitch or voice cues are helpful to separate the target from interfering speakers, whereas in tonal languages pitch also contains information important to distinguish word meaning. Therefore, impairments on pitch cues may have a more crucial effect on CMNS than on GS listeners.

Comparison of the vocoded and non-vocoded results suggests that reverberation has a more pronounced effect on

the SRTs of CMNS BiCI users than GS BiCI users. The absence of a significant SRM difference between the two simulated BiCI groups was expected, given the lack of SRM in symmetrically positioned maskers for both groups.

C. Speech cue analysis and speech perception

Figure 4 shows AM spectra of CMN and OLSA target sentences. One may question why only envelope power of the target, without interfering maskers, is shown. This can be justified by the fact that both the stationary SSN and the fluctuating IFFM were identical for both groups. Consequently, differences in the AM properties of the target signals are likely the most relevant. A comparison of the AM spectra of CMNS and GS material for R1, R2, and R3 in Fig. 4 revealed a stronger decrease in the (average) envelope power of German than of Chinese-Mandarin sentences as reverberation increases. However, neither for SSN nor for IFFM a more detrimental effect of reverberation on German than on Mandarin was observed in data. Thus, effects of reverberation on the envelope power of clean speech material (without masker) are not a sufficient predictor for speech intelligibility in this study. Figure 2(a) shows consistently lower SRTs for the CMNS compared to the GS group. In contrast, the AM spectra in Fig. 4 show, in most cases, higher envelope power for the GS group than for the CMNS group. This implies that envelope-power-based speech intelligibility models (e.g., Jørgensen and Dau, 2011; Jørgensen *et al.*, 2013) would fail to make accurate predictions, as they would predict lower SRTs for GS than for CMNS group, which does not align with the measured SRTs. This was confirmed by an informal test with 10 target sentences, where predictions based on the envelope-power pathway in the speech intelligibility model of Biberger and Ewert (2016) resulted in about 1.3 dB lower SRTs for OLSA sentences in the presence of co-located stationary SSN maskers in anechoic, compared to the CMNS-sentences with the same maskers. Therefore, modifications or additional cues would be required to adapt such models, designed for non-tonal speech, to account for tonal speech. However, this is beyond the scope of the current work.

The spectrograms in Fig. 1 show a substantially stronger spectro-temporal smearing for the CMN sentences presented in room R3 with moderate to strong reverberation than for the room with mild reverberation (R2) and the anechoic room (R1). Similarly, the pitch histograms of Mandarin CMN sentences in Fig. 5 also reveal a pronounced impairment due to reverberation, such as a significantly reduced pitch range. In contrast, the pitch histograms of OLSA sentences and IFFM seem to be less affected by reverberation. This pitch analysis may provide insight into why Mandarin-speaking listeners experience greater difficulty when speech with co-located IFFM is presented in rooms with moderate to strong reverberation, compared to German-speaking listeners.

However, it is important to note that the pitch results in reverberation shown in Figs. 1 and 5 rely on the accuracy of

the STRAIGHT pitch extraction algorithm, which may be even less reliable in noisy and reverberation conditions. Figure 1 shows that the example Mandarin sentence exhibits a wider F0 range (~100–330 Hz) than the OLSA sentence (~150–280 Hz) in the anechoic room, consistent with the findings of Traunmüller and Eriksson (1995). A similar trend is also observed in the pitch histogram derived from the ~1-min connected speech samples in Fig. 5. The peak at 150 Hz in the histogram of Fig. 5 is slightly lower than the average F0 of the sentence shown in Fig. 1, partly because the sentences in Figs. 1 and 5 come from different test lists. Nonetheless, the average pitch of the Mandarin sentences remains higher than the OLSA sentences. The results shown in Figs. 1 and 5 underscore potential limitations of the STRAIGHT algorithm in such challenging environments, especially considering that the human auditory system is remarkably robust in extracting pitch information, even under adverse noise conditions (e.g., Wang and Xu, 2020).

V. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to investigate potential differences in SRT and SRM between GS and CMNS listeners in noisy and reverberant environments. Both language groups were tested using the corresponding matrix sentence tests, with maskers that were either spatially separated from or co-located with the target speaker, under both non-vocoded and vocoded conditions.

On average, increasing reverberation time led to higher SRTs and smaller SRM, as expected. Reverberation had a stronger effect on SRTs and SRM for the IFFM than for the SSN. Both groups achieved significantly better SRTs and greater SRM in non-vocoded conditions compared to the corresponding vocoded conditions. In the vocoded conditions, there were no significant group differences in both SRTs and SRM, although CMNS listeners exhibited significantly lower SRTs in the anechoic room in most cases and in the small reverberant room for the symmetrically positioned IFFM maskers.

In the non-vocoded tests, under anechoic conditions, both language groups benefited from “listen into dips” as indicated by lower SRTs with fluctuating maskers (IFFM) than with stationary maskers (SSN). However, this release from masking was substantially reduced in reverberant rooms, even becoming negative due to the stronger impact of reverberation on SRTs and SRM in IFFM than in SSN, especially in the large reverberant room.

Across all the rooms, CMNS listeners showed significantly lower SRTs than GS listeners, with the difference being more pronounced for IFFM than SSN. Strong reverberation had a greater detrimental effect on CMNS groups ability to separate the target from the co-located maskers compared to the GS group, supporting Hypothesis 1. However, the contribution of the lower SRTs observed in the CMNS listeners in anechoic conditions and the greater acoustic similarity between the OLSA sentences and IFFM compared to the CMN sentences could not be ruled out.

There was no significant overall SRM difference between the two groups.

Regarding Hypothesis 2, AM spectra in the technical evaluation showed a larger AM depth in German than in Mandarin speech material under both anechoic and reverberant conditions. Despite this, CMNS listeners still achieved significantly lower SRTs than GS listeners in reverberant rooms for both SSN and IFFM. This suggests that AM spectra alone do not fully account for the better speech intelligibility of CMNS listeners compared to GS listeners. Consequently, speech intelligibility models based solely on AM cues may require additional parameters, such as pitch or TFS, to better predict the effect of maskers and reverberation on tonal languages.

Supporting Hypothesis 3, CI processing appears to have a more substantial impact on the SRTs of CMNS than on GS listeners, especially in IFFM conditions. However, in anechoic conditions, CMNS CI listeners showed lower SRTs than GS CI listeners, while in reverberant conditions, the differences were not significant. This pattern suggests that reverberation still has a more pronounced impact on the SRTs of CMNS CI users, even for the heavily degraded speech signal after CI processing, slightly deviating. However, caution is needed when interpreting these findings regarding Hypothesis 3, given the substantial individual variability among CI users, even within the same language. Further studies with a larger sample size and real CI users are necessary for more conclusive results.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

This study has an approval of the Ethics Committee of the University of Oldenburg (Drs.EK/2019/075). The relevant data within the paper will be available online.

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